

Gene flow and spontaneous mutations are responsible for imidazolinone herbicide-resistant weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)[☆]

Rasim Unan^{a,*}, Ozgur Azapoglu^b, İlyas Deligoz^b, Husrev Mennan^c, Kassim Al-Khatib^{a,*}

^a Department of Plant Science, University of California, Davis, 95616, CA, USA

^b Black Sea Agricultural Research Institute, Samsun, Türkiye

^c Plant Protection Department, Ondokuzmayıs University, Samsun, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Gene flow
Herbicide resistant crops
Imazamox
Spontaneous mutation
Weedy rice

ABSTRACT

For more than two decades, weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) has been controlled in rice fields by using imidazolinone (IMI) herbicide-resistant rice technology (Clearfield®). Outcrossing in weedy rice populations and spontaneous mutations are potential problems with herbicide-resistant crop management technologies, such as the IMI-resistant rice. The aim of this study was to characterize the mechanism of IMI herbicide resistance in weedy rice through dose-response bioassay study and evaluating amino acid substitutions in acetolactate synthase (ALS) protein. A total of 118 suspected IMI-resistant weedy rice samples, which survived in the field after an IMI herbicide application, were collected at harvest time from Türkiye in 2020 and 2021. Single-dose imazamox application experiment revealed that 38 plants survived herbicide treatment. The imazamox resistance of the surviving plants was confirmed by dose-response experiment. ALS gene region underwent a sanger DNA partial sequencing. No substitution was found in 10 samples, however, amino acid substitutions were found in 26 samples with S563N, one sample with S653T, and one sample with E630D. The S653N point is the same substitution point that serves as the origin of resistance for the Clearfield® rice varieties that are commonly cultivated in the region. It has been hypothesized that the gene flow from IMI-resistant rice may be the cause of resistance in the IMI resistant weedy rice samples with S653N. The other substitution, S653T, were considered spontaneous mutation to IMI resistance. Interestingly, the S653T mutation was detected for the first time in weedy rice. The mechanism of resistance of 10 resistant weedy rice was not confirmed in this study, however, it may be a non-target resistance or another mutation point in target site, but evidently, they did not acquire resistance by gene flow from IMI-resistant rice. It has been concluded that the effectiveness of IMI-resistant rice technology in controlling weedy rice has drastically decreased due to possible gene flow, spontaneous mutation and non-target resistance. In addition to cultural controls like clean seed, clean machinery and crop rotation, other herbicide-tolerant rice systems such as Provisia® and Roxy-RPS® rice are needed to create a diverse weedy rice management ensemble available for rice production and move towards sustainable rice farming.

1. Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a staple crop worldwide. While 90% of rice production is from Asian countries, European countries such as Italy, Türkiye, Spain, Greece, Portugal, France, and Bulgaria have significant rice production that contribute to the region's economy and culture (FAO, 2021). Türkiye produces one million tons of rice annually in an area of 129,475 ha with average yield of 7.72 t ha⁻¹ (FAO, 2021). Japonica rice varieties are dominating in Türkiye and rice production is centered around the Thrace-Marmara and the Black Sea regions. Türkiye

has a suitable environment conditions for rice production in the months of May to October and farmers use the direct pregerminated wet seeding planting method (Surek, 2002).

European including Türkiye farmers have a common practice of monoculture rice farming due to economic concerns and their cultivation traditions (Ferrero and Vidotto, 2010). Monoculture farming usually accompanies with some cultivation issues (Kraehmer et al., 2017). Monoculture rice farming may result in a set of weeds that are well adapted and highly competitive with rice plants. In addition, rice monoculture may result in development of herbicide resistant weeds

[☆] This paper was presented in part the V. International Conference on Agricultural, Biological and Life Science in 2023.

* Corresponding authors at: Department of Plant Sciences, MS4, One Shields Avenue, University of California, Davis, CA 95616, USA.

E-mail address: kalkhatib@ucdavis.edu (K. Al-Khatib).

(Ceskeski et al., 2022; Hill et al., 2006).

Weeds are important challenge of monoculture rice farming. The most common weeds in Türkiye monocultured rice fields are *Echinochloa crus galli* (L.) P.Beauv, *Echinochloa oryzoides* (Ard) Fritsch, *Echinochloa oryzicola* (Vasinger) Vasinger, *Alisma plantago aquatica* L., *Cyperus difformis* L. *Paspalum paspalodes* (Michx.) Schrib, *Lathyrus* spp. and weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) (Altop et al., 2015; Isik et al., 2000; Mennan and Kaya-Altop, 2012). Herbicides are important tool for weed management in rice (Yasuor et al., 2008). Intensive monoculture has encouraged the use of same herbicides and often the same mode of action herbicides (Ofosu et al., 2023) that resulted in rapid emergence of herbicide resistant weeds, particularly in the absence of any other weed management strategies.

Another problem with monoculture rice farming is weedy rice infestation (Altop et al., 2022). Weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a troublesome weed in rice fields and is extremely difficult to control with standard herbicides due to its botanical similarity to cultivated rice (De Leon et al., 2019). Weedy rice is highly competitive plant with ability to grow in diverse environmental conditions including cold weather conditions, (Galvin et al., 2023; Surek et al., 2014). Additional factors contributing to weed rice's problematic status in rice production were its numerous yearly lifecycles, high capacity for seed dissemination, significant intraspecific phenotypic variation, and elevated genetic diversity (Chauhan, 2013; Xia et al., 2011; Ziska et al., 2015). The characteristics that differentiate weedy rice from cultivar rice are higher seed shattering rate, longer seed dormancy, taller plants, and more tillers (Kanapeckas et al., 2018). Weedy rice causes significant damage in rice fields by interfering with cultivated rice growth. For example the red rice competition in Arkansas cost \$274 ha⁻¹ of damage to the state's rice crop in 2006 (Burgos et al., 2008).

IMI-resistant rice, also referred to as Clearfield®, is a cultivated rice tolerant to IMI herbicides that has made it possible to control weedy rice in post-emergence herbicide applications (Croughan et al., 1996). IMI herbicides inhibit ALS (EC 4.1.3.18) enzyme that catalyze the first step of branched chain amino acids synthesis, isoleucine, leucine, and valine. ALS protein, is the target site of IMI herbicides such as imazamox, imazapic, imazaquin, and imazethapyr. The Clearfield® rice cultivars were developed using traditional plant breeding methods natural selection following ALS gene-induced mutation. IMI herbicide resistance is caused by single nucleotide alterations at codon 653 and 654 of the ALS gene, which result in the substitution S653N and G654E (Scarabel et al., 2012; Tan et al., 2005). The earliest Clearfield® cultivars, CL121 and CL141, contained a G654E substitution; however, CL161 variety with S653N substitution was released in 2003 due to higher level of IMI herbicide resistance. The majority of later Clearfield® cultivars contain S653N substitution (Rajguru et al., 2005).

Clearfield® technology has been rapidly adopted by rice growers. Since the release of Clearfield® technology, many assessments of its benefits and detriments have been reported (Sudianto et al., 2013; Burgos et al., 2014; Avila et al., 2021). The benefits of IMI-rice cultivars were effective weed and increasing rice profitability (Merotto Jr et al., 2016). One of the detriments is failure of weedy rice and other weed control a few years after IMI herbicide application in Clearfield® rice fields is likely due to development of IMI herbicide resistance. Suspect target site is common mechanism to resistance to ALS in weedy rice biotypes that may be caused by spontaneous mutations or from cross pollination with IMI rice (Tranel and Wright, 2002; Sales et al., 2008).

Suspected weedy rice survivors to imazamox have been reported by farmers in Türkiye within a few years of its introduction. This study aimed to characterize resistance mechanisms present in weedy rice seed samples from Türkiye that survived an IMI herbicide application in the field, and determine if gene flow from Clearfield® rice or spontaneous mutation points caused IMI herbicide resistance in weedy rice.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant materials and seed source

The plant materials used in the study were classified in four categories; suspected IMI-resistant weedy rice, susceptible weedy rice, cultivated IMI-resistant rice and conventional rice (IMI-susceptible). The suspected IMI-resistant weedy rice biotypes were collected from IMI-resistant rice cultivar fields which survived the grower herbicide applications during the 2020 and 2021 growing season in northern Türkiye. The field locations were in Bafra Valley (41°36'08"N, 35°55'16"E) and Terme Valley (41°08'13"N, 37°02'45"E) in Samsun Province. A total of 118 weedy rice biotypes were collected. Three representative weedy rice biotypes were harvested from each 39 rice fields (except one field: four biotypes were collected in a field only) during seed collecting. The harvested weedy rice seeds were placed in paper bags, dried, threshed, and then stored at 4 °C. The seeds of the susceptible weedy rice biotype provided by Black Sea Agricultural Research Institute (BSARI). IMI-resistant rice varieties (Luna CL, Rekor CL, Iskender CL, Ozgur CL and Kopru CL) and a conventional rice variety (Kocamaninci) were provided by BSARI genetic stock as well. A dormancy characteristic is not present in IMI resistant and susceptible cultivated rice variety seeds. Weedy rice biotype seeds, however, were placed in paper envelopes and incubated for five days at 50 °C in a dry, dark environment to break dormancy (Galvin et al., 2022).

2.2. Single-dose evaluation experiment

Five seeds of the same biotypes that had already germinated were then transplanted into a single 8 by 10 by 6 cm pot with three replicates. For the course of the experiment, pots were set inside trays filled with water to keep the soil moist in the pots. The sterilized medium soil used in the greenhouse tests was made up of 1.23 kg m⁻² of dolomite, 1/3 volume compost (redwood shavings and turkey manure), 1/3 volume coarse sand, and 1/3 volume peat moss. The seedlings were placed in a greenhouse and watered as-needed. Greenhouse conditions were maintained at 26 to 36 °C day/night temperatures. At 3 to 4 leaf stage, imazamox ((+)-2-(4-isopropyl-4-methyl-5-oxo-2-imidazolin-2-yl)-5-(methoxymethyl) nicotinic acid) was applied using an automatic sprayer chamber (Technical Machinery Incorporated, USA) calibrated to deliver 187 L ha⁻¹ at 275 kPa. Imazamox (Imox, 12.1% ai; Alligare LLC, Alabama, USA) rate was 106 g ha⁻¹ (2× labeled rate) mixed with 0.25%v (v/v) nonionic surfactant (0.25% v/v NIS). Visual evaluation of plant survival was performed 28 days after herbicide application. Plants with new green leaf growth and had <10% of chlorotic leaves were classified as suspected resistant, but plants that had no new growth and had >50% of chlorotic leaves were classified as susceptible (Roso et al., 2010).

2.3. Dose-response experiment

The evaluate the resistance level of the weedy rice biotypes to imazamox A total of 38 biotypes of weedy rice that survived the 106 g ai ha⁻¹ rate application of imazamox, susceptible population of weedy rice, IMI-resistant cultivated rice and conventional rice were included in the dose-response study. Plants treated with imazamox as described above. Imazamox application rates were 0, 13.25, 26.5, 53, 106, 212, 424, and 848 g ai ha⁻¹. Dryweight of aboveground biomass was measured 28 days after treatment (DAT). Each treatment was replicated three times.

2.4. Nucleotide substitution experiment

A molecular study was conducted to determine the mutation points that cause IMI-resistance in weedy rice. Thirty-eight weedy rice, one susceptible weedy rice biotype, five IMI resistant rice variety, and one IMI susceptible conventional rice variety were analyzed. Three samples

from each biotypes/varieties were tested. At 28 DAT, fresh leaf tissue was obtained from each weedy rice biotypes. DNA was extracted using the CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) technique (Doyle and Doyle, 1987). From the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) a primer pair was created as forward TCCGCATGAGAACCTCCCTGTG and reverse AGATTAATACACAGTCCCTGCCATC. The Qiagen Taq PCR master mix (Qiagen, N.V., Netherlands), which contains 25 μ L of TAQ Master mix, 1 μ L of each primer (10 M), and 1 μ L of genomic DNA mixed in ddH₂O in 50 μ L, was used to perform polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification. Thermal processing was used, starting with a denaturing phase at 95 °C for 5 min, then 35 cycles of 45 s denaturation at 95 °C, 45 s annealing at 60 °C, 60 s elongation at 72 °C, and finally a final extension of 5 min at 72 °C. For one hour, electrophoresis was carried out at 110 V. The QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, N.V. Nederland) was used to isolate plant DNA. At a private genomics facility, sequencing was carried out. MEGA software was used to examine the sequencing data.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The rate of each herbicide that results in a 50% reduction in dry weight (ED₅₀) was determined using the four-parameter log-logistic model (Seefeldt et al., 1995). The R software DRC package (v4.3-1; Ritz et al., 2015) was used for statistical analysis to calculate the ED₅₀ estimates.

$$Y = C + \frac{D - C}{1 + \exp(b(\log(x) - \log(ED_{50})))}$$

Where b represents the slope around the ED₅₀, C and D represent the lower and upper asymptote limits, respectively, and represents the herbicide dose. The lowest bound, C , of the asymptote was set to zero in this analysis. Fitted dose response curves based on different independent variables at each time point were compared among weedy rice biotypes by contrasting the best fit values using one-way ANOVA. Since there were no significant differences between the repeated experiments ($p >$

0.001), the results were combined. The Resistance Index (RI) was calculated by dividing the ED₅₀ of the resistant biotype by the susceptible biotype (Guo et al., 2016).

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Single-dose evaluation experiment

In total, 80 weedy rice biotypes were killed at the 106 g ai ha⁻¹ (2 \times) imazamox rate. The other 38 biotypes of weedy rice were not injured by imazamox treatment. While five Clearfield® rice varieties were not affected by the application, the conventional variety Kocamaninci and susceptible control weedy rice biotype were killed by imazamox.

3.2. Dose-response experiment

The findings of the whole-plant dose-response bioassay revealed that there were no significant interactions between imazamox rate and weed rice resistant biotypes, therefore, the data were combined for the subsequent analysis. Imazamox resistance was very high in 38 weedy rice biotypes, where ED₅₀ value was recorded between 146.9 and 369.1 g ai ha⁻¹ imazamox (Table 1, Fig. 1). Likewise, Clearfield® rice varieties had high imazamox resistance with ED₅₀ values between 242.4 and 298.8 g ai ha⁻¹ imazamox (Table 1). On the other hand, ED₅₀ values for Kocamaninci conventional rice variety and susceptible control weedy rice imazamox resistance were 18.6 and 15.1 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively. RI was 24.4 for weedy rice biotype 118, however, RI was considerably low as 1.2 for conventional rice variety Kocamaninci (Table 1). RI was also as high as 19.8 for resistant variety Iskender CL (Table 1).

3.3. Nucleotide substitution experiment

The amplified fragment of the ALS amino acid sequence in weedy rice showed 99% similarity to the hypothetical protein of ALS OsJ_06870 (*Oryza sativa* Japonica Group) sequences. To find the

Fig. 1. Dose-response curve of weedy rice biotypes to imazamox. S was the susceptible weedy rice (control accession) had ED₅₀ level 15.1 g ai ha⁻¹ imazamox; R was the most resistant weedy rice (accession number 118) had ED₅₀ level 369.1 g ai ha⁻¹ imazamox.

Table 1

Parameters of nonlinear regression of imazamox, the values of the rates needed to cause 50% injury (ED₅₀), and resistance index for weedy rice biotypes tested in the greenhouse.

Weedy Rice Biotype Number and Rice Variety	Amino Acid Substitution	Parameters				R index	
		B, Slope (SE)	C, Lower (SE)	D, Upper (SE)	ED ₅₀ (SE)	p value	
					g ai ha ⁻¹		
3	S653N	1.5(0.3)	19.1(8.9)	103.3(2.9)	148.4(32.7)	9.8	<0.001**
6	S653N	1.3(0.1)	19.8(4.3)	102.1(1.2)	187.3(20.9)	12.4	<0.001**
7	S653N	7.3 (2.5)	79.7(0.2)	100.0(0.1)	206.9(2.2)	13.7	<0.001**
9	S653N	3.0(0.9)	78.3(1.7)	100.3(0.6)	223.2(26.3)	14.8	<0.001**
10	S653N	1.6(0.1)	56.1(2.2)	101.0(0.6)	219.8(19.2)	14.6	<0.001**
13	S653N	2.2(0.2)	66.3(1.7)	100.4(0.3)	317.4(22.5)	21.0	<0.001**
17	Non	1.7(0.1)	53.3(2.2)	100.9(0.5)	239.7(19.4)	15.9	<0.001**
20	S653N	1.7(0.2)	54.3(2.2)	101.0(0.6)	216.5(18.5)	14.3	<0.001**
25	S653N	1.6(0.1)	55.1(2.4)	100.9(0.6)	245.1(23.1)	16.2	<0.001**
26	S653N	1.8(0.1)	44.5(2.4)	100.8(0.7)	23.6(16.6)	15.6	<0.001**
27	S653N	1.5(0.1)	54.4(2.5)	101.4(0.6)	234.4(23.1)	15.5	<0.001**
28	S653N	3.2(0.3)	43.1(1.2)	100.4(0.7)	163.7(5.98)	10.8	<0.001**
29	Non	2.2(0.1)	36.6(1.0)	100.6(0.3)	216.6(5.4)	14.3	<0.001**
30	S653N	1.6(0.2)	36.7(3.4)	101.1(0.8)	242.1(22.1)	16.0	<0.001**
31	S653N	1.9(0.1)	39.5(1.5)	100.7(0.4)	237.1(9.2)	15.7	<0.001**
38	Non	1.6(0.1)	36.3(3.6)	101.1(0.9)	246.1(23.5)	16.3	<0.001**
40	S653N	2.1(0.1)	41.9(3.7)	100.8(0.7)	334.1(29.2)	22.1	<0.001**
41	Non	2.1(0.1)	36.7(1.1)	100.7(0.3)	217.8(5.6)	14.4	<0.001**
42	S653N	3.1(0.3)	41.9(1.2)	100.4(0.7)	166.5(5.7)	11.0	<0.001**
51	S653N	3.0(0.2)	48.5(1.2)	100.5(0.4)	253.7(8.6)	16.8	<0.001**
52	S653N	1.7(0.2)	47.8(3.0)	101.6(1.1)	161.8(17.7)	10.7	<0.001**
58	E630D	2.4(0.2)	69.4(1.3)	100.4(0.3)	287.3(17.8)	19.0	<0.001**
71	S653N	3.1(0.7)	62.0(2.3)	100.6(0.7)	213.3(18.5)	14.1	<0.001**
72	Non	2.2(0.2)	49.8(1.5)	100.8(0.6)	184.7(9.8)	12.2	<0.001**
73	S653N	2.3(0.2)	67.5(1.3)	100.4(0.3)	311.5(17.9)	20.6	<0.001**
74	S653N	1.7(0.1)	25.8(3.7)	101.1(1.0)	234.2(19.4)	15.5	<0.001**
75	Non	1.9(0.1)	29.1(2.0)	100.4(1.1)	146.9(7.5)	9.7	<0.001**
76	S653N	1.3(0.1)	29.5(2.8)	101.4(0.7)	215.3(16.7)	14.3	<0.001**
77	S653N	1.1(0.1)	35.0(4.0)	101.8(0.9)	207.3(27.3)	13.7	<0.001**
79	Non	3.2(0.3)	51.6(1.2)	100.5(0.5)	233.2(8.3)	15.4	<0.001**
83	Non	3.3(0.1)	50.3(0.7)	100.3(0.2)	267.5(5.1)	17.7	<0.001**
84	Non	2.9(0.2)	48.6(1.5)	100.6(0.5)	250.8(10.3)	16.6	<0.001**
85	S653N	1.9(0.2)	36.9(3.0)	101.6(1.2)	159.4(13.6)	10.6	<0.001**
96	S653N	2.2(0.1)	32.0(3.1)	100.8(0.6)	333.9(21.1)	22.1	<0.001**
115	S653N	7.3(2.9)	43.8(1.1)	100.1(0.7)	185.3(10.0)	12.3	<0.001**
116	S653T	4.6(0.6)	29.4(2.3)	98.0(0.9)	295.5(12.9)	19.6	<0.001**
117	Non	5.1(0.1)	31.3(0.3)	100.0(0.1)	297.2(2.2)	19.7	<0.001**
118	S653N	2.0(0.2)	63.5(2.4)	100.4(0.3)	369.1(33.4)	24.4	<0.001**
Rekor CL	S653N	2.9(0.2)	48.7(1.4)	100.6(0.4)	249.1(9.7)	16.5	<0.001**
Kopru CL	S653N	3.0(0.2)	49.9(1.2)	100.5(0.4)	252.2(8.4)	16.7	<0.001**
Ozgur CL	S653N	3.6(1.6)	57.0(3.5)	100.5(1.4)	206.1(21.7)	13.6	<0.001**
Iskender CL	S653N	4.5(0.1)	39.5(0.2)	100.0(0.1)	298.8(1.8)	19.8	<0.001**
Luna CL	S653N	2.1(0.1)	48.3(1.1)	100.3(0.3)	242.4(7.7)	16.1	<0.001**
Kocamaninci	Non	1.2(0.1)	-2.1(0.6)	99.8(0.8)	18.6(0.4)	1.2	<0.001**
Susceptible W.Rice	Non	2.3(0.1)	0.4(0.6)	100.1(1.2)	15.1(0.3)	1.0	<0.001**

ED₅₀: effective dose to control half of test biotypes, B: Slope of the curve around the ED₅₀, C: Minimum level, D: Maximum level, SE: Standard error, R index: The resistance index was calculated the ED50 values of the resistant biotypes divided by the ED₅₀ values of the susceptible control weedy rice. ***Significant at the 0.001 probability level.

Fig. 2. ALS amino acid sequences of the amplified fragment of *Hypothetical protein OsJ_06870* (*Oryza sativa* L.), the susceptible (S) check weedy rice, resistant weedy rice (R) (accession number 118, 116, and 58), Clearfield rice variety (Iskender CL), conventional rice variety (Kocamaninci). The black boxes illustrated that amino acid substitution from serine (S) 653 to ASPARAGINE (N), and THREONINE (T) in weedy rice accession 118 and 116; and from GLUTAMIC ACID (E) 630 to ASPARTIC ACID (D) in weedy rice accession 58. The *Hypothetical protein OsJ_06870* (*Oryza sativa* L.) (from NCBI) and Iskender CL resistant to imazamox (S1) ALS sequence was used as reference.

resistance mechanism, a partial of the ALS fragment was amplified and sequenced. Comparing the sequences of the resistant populations, multiple significant amino acid substitution was determined in the ALS region (Table 1). There are several previous reports that showed weedy rice target site resistance to the IMI herbicide. It has been reported that the ALS protein mutations at A122, P197, A205, D376, W574, and S653 are most often to confer resistance to ALS inhibitors (Tranel and Wright, 2002; Whaley et al., 2004; Corbett and Tardif, 2006). In this study, three substitutions were discovered at two positions (Fig. 2). The substitution S653N were identified in the 26 weedy rice biotypes, and this substitution was also present in all tested Clearfield® varieties (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). The fact that the IMI resistant weedy rice biotypes with the S653N substitution are clearly different from the Clearfield® rice varieties and this differences was confirmed by the plant external appearance, such as plant height, awn/awnless kernel, grain shedding, hull color, and the red pericarp structure. A different amino acid substitution S653T was discovered at the same mutation point in one weedy rice biotype (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). Finally, a E630D amino acid substitution was found at a different point in a weedy rice biotype (Fig. 2, Fig. 4). No mutation was detected in the other 10 resistant weedy rice biotypes, susceptible check weedy rice, and conventional rice (Table 1). When evaluating all suspicious genotypes, the frequency of S653N, S653T, and E630D substitutions were 22.03%, 0.84% and 0.84%, respectively. On the other hand, when weedy rice biotypes determined to be resistance by dose-response study,

Fig. 3. Electropherograms from Sanger sequencing with boxes illustrate that substitution mutations at positions SERINE/S (AGT) 653 to ASPARAGINE/N (AAT) or THREONINE/T (ACT), where ALS herbicide, imazamox, confer resistance on weedy rice. At point 653, there is no substitution observed for susceptible check weedy rice, and Kocamaninci conventional rice variety. The *Hypothetical protein OsJ_06870* (*Oryza sativa* L.) (from NCBI) and susceptible weedy rice (S) ALS sequence was used as reference.

Fig. 4. Electropherograms from Sanger sequencing with boxes illustrate that substitution mutations at positions GLUTAMIC ACID/E (GAG) 630 to ASPARTIC ACID/D (GAT) in weedy rice. The point 630 substitution was exist only accession 58 weedy rice. The *Hypothetical protein OsJ_06870* (*Oryza sativa* L.) (from NCBI) and susceptible weedy rice (S) ALS sequence was used as reference.

the frequency of S653N, S653T, and E630D were 68.42%, 2.63% and 2.63%, respectively. These findings suggested that the target site resistance mechanism in the associated IMI-resistant weedy rice biotypes was caused by these key substitutions.

The S653N mutation was detected in 26 resistant weedy rice biotypes used in the study. This mutation point is also the mutation point that provides resistance to Clearfield® rice. Earlier researchers showed that S653N substitution as the main mechanism of resistance in weedy rice (Scarabel et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2017; Wedger et al., 2022; Rajguru et al., 2005). The S653N mutation, which provides resistance to IMI herbicides, was identified in some other weeds in addition to weedy rice such as *Amaranthus palmeri* (Palmieri et al., 2022), *Amaranthus tuberculatus* (Patzoldt and Tranel, 2007), *Avena fatua* (Torres-Garcia et al., 2018), *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Chang and Duggleby, 1998), and other common crops such as *Triticum aestivum* L. (Ellison et al., 2013). The earlier research also determined that the source of resistance is most likely from outcross pollination with gene flow from the Clearfield varieties. Considering that Clearfield® technology has been available in the region for <10 years, resistant weedy rice is an important problem that needs to be addressed carefully especially if other resistant traits introduced to rice.

The other mutation point S653T recorded, which is in the same responsible point (ALS amino acid 653) in Clearfield® rice but different amino acid substitution from S653N (Fig. 2). The S653T substitution has

been reported in plants such as *Amaranthus tuberculatus* and *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Corbett and Tardif, 2006; Patzoldt and Tranel, 2007), but to our knowledge the S653T was not previously reported in weedy rice. The S653T mutations are considered spontaneous mutations because they would have developed through selection pressure and not gene flow from Clearfield rice (Corbett and Tardif, 2006; Patzoldt and Tranel, 2007; Rajguru et al., 2005; Sales et al., 2008;). Kuk et al. (2008) stated that IMI-resistant weedy rice probably existed before Clearfield® rice varieties were introduced. The hypothesis of spontaneous mutations confer to IMI resistance was confirmed in some weedy rice accessions in Türkiye.

The weedy rice accession number 58 had an E630D amino acid substitution. The E630D was previously reported in weedy rice (Rajguru et al., 2005). In this study, E630D mutation was detected in IMI-resistant weedy rice but it is unclear whether it is associated with IMI tolerance. Sales et al. (2008) presumed that the E630D stated may not be associated with IMI resistance in weedy rice due to observed in susceptible weedy rice. The structural orientation of the herbicide binding to ALS, explains why E630D is not a functional mutation for IMI resistance in some study (Yean et al., 2021).

The resistance mechanism of 10 resistant weedy rice used in the study could not be determined (Table 1), however, they clearly did not gain resistance through gene flow from Clearfield® rice. The source of resistance may be other gene regions that have not been scanned, and there is also the possibility of non-target resistance. This result was supported by other reported that showed off-target site resistance might be an alternate molecular mechanism in IMI-resistant weedy rice, as demonstrated by a combination of ALS gene sequencing, enzyme colorimetric assay, and genome-wide association study (Yean et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

The amino acid substitution in most IMI-resistant weedy rice was similar to the substitution found in Clearfield® rice, which provides evidence to suggest gene flow assisted in promoting the herbicide resistance trait to weedy rice. However, a small proportion of spontaneous mutations were identified among the tested weedy rice biotypes. Additionally, the source of IMI-resistance in some weedy rice biotypes could not be determined. IMI-resistant weedy rice is prevalent in Türkiye's rice 2012 growing region decreasing the viability of Clearfield® technology for weedy rice control. Therefore, diverse weedy rice management tools are needed to avoid further selection pressure for resistant biotypes. Sustainable rice farming will need to be accomplished with successful weedy rice management techniques, which can include crop rotations, imazamox spraying twice in Clearfield® rice (Milan et al., 2017), certificated clean seeds, clean machinery when going field to field, spot spraying (Unan et al., 2023), stale seedbed technique (Dilipkumar et al., 2022) and also leaving rice fields flooded after harvest (Pala et al., 2023). Our research findings can help to the risks associated with potential future herbicide-resistant rice technologies like Provisia® and Roxy-RPS® Rice in rice production fields. Rice farmers need more herbicide-resistant technologies to control weedy rice but also to have proper stewardship of their use.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rasim Unan: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ozgur Azapoglu:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft. **İlyas Deligoz:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology. **Husrev Mennan:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Kassim Al-Khatib:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [897192], (project HerbaRice). No competing interests have been declared.

References

- Altop, E., Mennan, H., Haghnama, K., 2015. Invasion of *Oryza sativa* L. (redrice) and *Echinochloa oryzicola* vasinger (latewatergrass) in rice cultivation. *Turk. J. Weed Sci.* 18, 32–35.
- Altop, E., Uysal, M.S., Haghnama, K., Mennan, H., 2022. Environmental factors on seasonal germination of different weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) biotypes. *Cienc. Rural* 53, e20210728.
- Avila, L., Marchesan, E., Camargo, E., Merotto, A., Ulguim, A., Noldin, J., Andres, A., Mariot, C., Agostinetto, D., Dornolles, S., Markus, C., 2021. Eighteen years of Clearfield™ rice in Brazil: what have we learned? *Weed Sci.* 69 (5), 585–597.
- Burgos, N.R., Norsworthy, J.K., Scott, R.C., Smith, K.L., 2008. Red rice status after five years of Clearfield™ rice. *Weed Technol.* 22, 200–208.
- Burgos, N.R., Singh, V., Tseng, T.M., Black, H., Young, N.D., Huang, Z., Hyma, K.E., Gealy, D.R., Caicedo, A.L., 2014. The impact of herbicide-resistant rice technology on phenotypic diversity and population structure of United States weedy rice. *Plant Physiol.* 166 (3), 1208–1220.
- Ceskeski, A.R., Godar, A.S., Al-Khatib, K., 2022. The stale-drill establishment method for rice: weed community, rice stand development, and yield components of two vigorous japonica cultivars. *Field Crop Res.* 276, 108369.
- Chang, A.K., Duggleby, R.G., 1998. Herbicide-resistant forms of *Arabidopsis thaliana* acetohydroxyacid synthase: characterization of the catalytic properties and sensitivity to inhibitors of four defined mutants. *Biochem. J.* 333 (3), 765–777.
- Chauhan, B.S., 2013. Strategies to manage weedy rice in Asia. *Crop Prot.* 48, 51–56.
- Corbett, C.L., Tardif, F.J., 2006. Detection of resistance to acetolactate synthase inhibitors in weeds with emphasis on DNA-based techniques: a review. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 62, 584–597.
- Croughan, T.P., Utomo, H.S., Sanders, D.E., Braverman, M.P., 1996. Herbicide-resistant rice offers potential solution to red rice problem. *La Agric.* 39, 10–12.
- De Leon, T.B., Karn, E., Al-Khatib, K., Espino, L., Blank, T., Andaya, C.B., Andaya, V.C., Brim-DeForest, W., 2019. Genetic variation and possible origins of *O. sativa* spontanea found in California. *Ecol. Evol.* 9 (10), 5835–5848.
- Dilipkumar, M., Mohamad-Ghazali, M., Shari, E., Lee Chuen, N., Chauhan, B., Chuah, T., 2022. Integrated use of the stale seedbed technique with preemergence herbicides to control weedy rice in wet seeded rice. *Weed Technol.* 36 (3), 373–378.
- Doyle, J.J., Doyle, J.L., 1987. A rapid DNA isolation procedure for small quantities of fresh leaf tissue. *Phytochem. Bull.* 19, 11–15.
- Ellison, M.T., Fischinger, F., Zemetra, R.S., Kuhl, J.C., 2013. Use of pyrosequencing technology to genotype imidazolinone-tolerant wheat. *Crop Sci.* 53 (5), 2021–2027.
- FAO, 2021. Food and Agriculture Organization. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>.
- Ferrero, A., Vidotto, F., 2010. 11 History of Rice in Europe. *Rice: Origin, Antiquity and History*, p. 341.
- Galvin, L., Inci, D., Mesgaran, M., Brim-DeForest, W., Al-Khatib, K., 2022. Flooding depths and burial effects on seedling emergence of five California weedy rice (*Oryza sativa spontanea*) accessions. *Weed Sci.* 2, 213–219.
- Galvin, L.B., DeLong, M.T., Al-Khatib, K., 2023. Utilizing germinability thresholds for optimizing stale seedbed applications to control red rice (*Oryza* spp) in California rice cropping systems. *Weed Technol.* 37, 15–20.
- Guo, W.L., Lv, L.L., Zhang, L.L., Li, Q., Wu, C.X., Lu, X.T., Liu, W., Wang, J., 2016. Herbicides cross resistance of a multiple resistant shortawn foxtail (*Alopecurus aequalis* Sobol.) population in wheat field. *Chil. J. Agric. Res.* 76, 163–169.
- Hill, J.E., Williams, J.F., Muters, R.G., Greer, C.A., 2006. The California rice cropping system: agronomic and natural resource issues for long-term sustainability. *Paddy Water Environ.* 4, 13–19.
- Isik, D., Mennan, H., Ecevit, O., 2000. Determination of wild species in rice fields in Samsun province. *Anadolu J. Agric. Sci.* 15 (3), 99–104.
- Kanapeckas, K.L., Tseng, T.M., Vigueira, C.C., Ortiz, A., Bridges, W.C., Burgos, N.R., Fischer, A.J., Lawton-Rauh, A., 2018. Contrasting patterns of variation in weedy traits and unique crop features in divergent populations of US weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* sp.) in Arkansas and California. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 74, 1404–1415.
- Kraehmer, H., Thomas, C., Vidotto, F., 2017. Rice production in Europe. In: Chauhan, B., Jabran, K., Mahajan, G. (Eds.), *Rice Production Worldwide*. Springer, Cham, pp. 95–116.
- Kuk, Y.I., Burgos, N.R., Shivrain, V.K., 2008. Natural tolerance to imazethapyr in red rice (*Oryza sativa*). *Weed Sci.* 56 (1), 1–11.

- Mennan, H., Kaya-Altup, E., 2012. Molecular techniques for discrimination of late watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzicola*) and early watergrass (*Echinochloa oryzoides*) species in Turkish rice production. *Weed Sci.* 60 (4), 525–530.
- Merotto Jr., A., Goulart, I.C., Nunes, A.L., Kalsing, A., Markus, C., Menezes, V.G., Wander, A.E., 2016. Evolutionary and social consequences of introgression of nontransgenic herbicide resistance from rice to weedy rice in Brazil. *Evol. Appl.* 9 (7), 837–846.
- Milan, M., Ferrero, A., Fogliatto, S., DePalo, F., Vidotto, F., 2017. Imazamox dissipation in two rice management systems. *J. Agric. Sci.* 155 (3), 431–443.
- Ofosu, R., Agyemang, E.D., Márton, A., Pásztor, G., Taller, J., Kazinczi, G., 2023. Herbicide resistance: managing weeds in a changing world. *Agronomy*. 13 (6), 1595.
- Pala, F., Mennan, H., Jabran, K., 2023. Competitive ability of imidazolinone-tolerant rice (cv. Luna) with different weedy rice (*Oryza sativa* f. spontanea) biotypes. *Phytoparasitica* 1–12.
- Palmieri, V.E., Alvarez, C.E., Permingeat, H.R., Perotti, V.E., 2022. A122S, A205V, D376E, W574L and S653N substitutions in acetolactate synthase (ALS) from *Amaranthus palmeri* show different functional impacts on herbicide resistance. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 78 (2), 749–757.
- Patzoldt, W.L., Tranel, P.J., 2007. Multiple ALS mutations confer herbicide resistance in waterhemp (*Amaranthus tuberculatus*). *Weed Sci.* 55, 421–428.
- Rajguru, S.N., Burgos, N.R., Shivrain, V.K., Stewart, J.M., 2005. Mutations in the red rice ALS gene associated with resistance to imazethapyr. *Weed Sci.* 53 (5), 567–577.
- Ritz, C., Baty, F., Streibig, J.C., Gerhard, D., 2015. Dose-response analysis using R. *PLoS One* 10 (12), e0146021.
- Roso, A.C., Merotto Jr., A., Delatorre, C.A., Menezes, V.G., 2010. Regional scale distribution of imidazolinone herbicide-resistant alleles in red rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) determined through SNP markers. *Field Crop Res.* 119 (1), 175–182.
- Sales, M.A., Shivrain, V.K., Burgos, N.R., Kuk, Y.I., 2008. Amino acid substitutions in the acetolactate synthase gene of red rice (*Oryza sativa*) confer resistance to imazethapyr. *Weed Sci.* 56, 485–489.
- Scarabel, L., Cenghialta, C., Manuello, D., Sattin, M., 2012. Monitoring and management of imidazolinone-resistant red rice (*Oryza sativa* L., var. *svlvatica*) in Clearfield® Italian Paddy Rice. *Agronomy*. 2 (4), 371–383.
- Seefeldt, S.S., Jensen, J.E., Fuerst, E.P., 1995. Log-logistic analysis of herbicide dose-response relationships. *Weed Technol.* 9, 218–227.
- Singh, V., Singh, S., Black, H., Boyett, V., Basu, S., Gealy, D., Gbur, E., Pereira, A., Scott, R.C., Caicedo, A., Burgos, N.R., 2017. Introgression of Clearfield™ rice crop traits into weedy red rice outcrosses. *Field Crop Res.* 207, 13–23.
- Sudianto, E., Beng-Kah, S., Ting-Xiang, N., Saldain, N.E., Scott, R.C., Burgos, N.R., 2013. Clearfield® rice: its development, success, and key challenges on a global perspective. *Crop Prot.* 49, 40–51.
- Surek, H., 2002. Rice Cultivation. Hasad Publication, Istanbul, Türkiye.
- Surek, H., Beser, N., Kaya, R., Unan, R., 2014. Rice breeding for herbicide resistance in Turkey. *Turk. J. Agric. Nat. Sci. Spec. Issue* 1, 1258–1263.
- Tan, S., Evans, R.R., Dahmer, M.L., Singh, B.K., Shaner, D.L., 2005. Imidazolinone-tolerant crops: history, current status and future. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 61, 246–257.
- Torres-Garcia, J.R., Tafuya-Razo, J.A., Velazquez-Marquez, S., Tiessen, A., 2018. Double herbicide-resistant biotypes of wild oat (*Avena fatua*) display characteristic metabolic fingerprints before and after applying ACCase-and ALS-inhibitors. *Acta Physiol. Plant.* 40, 1–12.
- Tranel, P.J., Wright, T.R., 2002. Resistance of weeds to ALS-inhibiting herbicides: what have we learned? *Weed Sci.* 50, 700–712.
- Unan, R., Galvin, L., Becerra-Alvarez, A., Al-Khatib, K., 2023. Assessing clethodim spot spraying applications for control of problematic weedy rice and other grasses in California rice fields. *Agron. J.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/agi2.21500>.
- Wedger, M.J., Roma-Burgos, N., Olsen, K.M., 2022. Genomic revolution of US weedy rice in response to 21st century agricultural technologies. *Commun. Biol.* 5 (1), 885.
- Whaley, C.M., Wilson, H.P., Westwood, J.H., 2004. Characterization of a new ALS-inhibitor resistance mutation from the ALS gene of smooth pigweed (*Amaranthus hybridus*). *Weed Sci. Soc. Am.* 44, 16.
- Xia, H.B., Xia, H., Ellstrand, N.C., Yang, C., Lu, B.R., 2011. Rapid evolutionary divergence and ecotypic diversification of germination behavior in weedy rice populations. *New Phytol.* 191 (4), 1119–1127.
- Yasuor, H., TenBrook, P.L., Tjeerdema, R.S., Fischer, A.J., 2008. Responses to clomazone and 5-ketoclomazone by *Echinochloa phyllopogon* resistant to multiple herbicides in Californian rice fields. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 64, 1031–1039.
- Yean, R.A., Dilipkumar, M., Rahman, S., Song, B.K., 2021. A two-in-one strategy: target and nontarget site mechanisms both play important role in IMI-resistant weedy rice. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 22 (3), 982.
- Ziska, L.H., Gealy, D.R., Burgos, N., Caicedo, A.L., Gressel, J., Lawton-Rauh, A.L., Avila, L.A., Theisen, G., Norsworthy, J., Ferrero, A., 2015. Weedy (red) rice: an emerging constraint to global rice production. *Adv. Agron.* 129, 181–228.